

Statement of the ReMO COST Action on solidarity with Ukraine

The ReMO COST Action stands in solidarity with the people of Ukraine. We add our voices to the [joint declaration](#) of Eurodoc and the Marie Curie Alumni Association and strongly condemn the Russian Federation's acts of violence and aggression against the people of Ukraine. We also concur with the [COST Association's call](#) for international efforts to help ensure the safety of Ukrainian researchers and innovators.

ReMO is a closely-knit network and we are deeply concerned about the safety of two of our network members based at the International Humanitarian University in Odessa.

There are practical ways that we can support displaced Ukrainian scientists:

1. If your lab is willing to support displaced Ukrainian scientists, please enter information on this [form](#).
2. Please ask your university/research institution/research funder to add itself to this [list](#) as being willing to provide funding, accommodation, visiting researcher status or any other form of help:
3. Support the [call of the Inspireurope partners](#) on European Governments and EU institutions to act quickly to support researchers at risk and to actively protect academic freedom against authoritarianism:
4. Support *ScienceforUkraine* at https://twitter.com/Sci_for_Ukraine and <http://scienceforukraine.eu/>

We keep in mind that the actions of the Russian regime are not representative of the Russian people and we welcome and support the [open letter from Russian academics and science journalists calling for peace](#).

Our COST Action is focussed on international cooperation and communication within Europe. We believe in inclusion, dialogue, peace, and support the advancement of society through education and research. We are deeply concerned about the physical and mental health and safety of the Ukrainian people, especially those most vulnerable, including the elderly, the children, and the sick. We call on the Russian Federation to cease its attack on Ukraine.

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